

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MOHAMMED****FIRST NAME: AUGUSTINE****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

List of 5 key concepts and page numbers in the:

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2019,1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Some rules of thumb for writing papers (EUCLID 2019,14-22)
4. What is style guide and why I need one? (EUCLID 2019, 24)
5. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27- 29)

IMPROVING MY ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS

1) INTRODUCTION

This is yet another academic challenge that is putting my knowledge to test for greater height. I have worked for the National Electoral Commission-Sierra Leone for about 13 years where all official correspondences both oral and writing communications are done in English. My job has to do with writing event reports, writing and making presentations, writing official letters, drawing Electoral timelines, sending emails and so on. I have two Masters Degrees and all I studied in English. To be explicit, all my academic studies have been done in English. The PhD program with EUCLID I am pursuing now has introduced me to a whole lot of new English writing skills and concepts. The use of Chicago-Turabian style, Zotero, Grammarly and so on is new concepts and practices to me altogether. I have to braise up to measure up to this new academic requirement.

The international academic writing been the first module has seven (7) periods scheduled. The first period has a study material supplied and a video of 14 minutes' length explaining the rules on the style to be adopted for the RP. Reading through the study material and following the video, I have realized that I am on the way to master the key concepts of essay writing, avoiding plagiarism, following the rules of writing papers, determining the clear line between American and English and so on thereby preparing me for a huge knowledge buildup and great research thesis.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Having essay writing as part of this study reminds me of Secondary/High School days when our teachers used to ask the classes at various levels to write essays on how we spent end of year holidays. Essay writing at every levels formed part of the school curriculum. Academic essay writing also transcended to my undergraduate and graduate studies where it was required to answer research questions or task. Before now and today, I had this believe that academic essay writing is a difficult task mainly because the reports I use to write has a structured and well-defined sections which is not so for essays. According to EUCLID (2019, 6) there is no precise definition of an essay, no prescription for what an essay, no prescription for what an essay should look like in terms of structure or content”

EUCLID (2019, 1) stated that:

An academic essay should answer a question or task.

- *It should have a thesis statement (answer to the question) and an argument.*
- *It should try to present or discuss something: to develop a thesis via a set of closely related points by reasoning and evidence.*
- *An academic essay should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from academic text or credible.*

The Academic Essay writing help build students’ knowledge. After readying the course pack and other books related to academic writing and doing this RP, I gradually understand the key concepts of analyzing and interpretation of data, filtering and shifting unwanted materials, use modern research skills and embracing critical thinking approach that will help my studies and beyond. Writing essays helps students to writes acceptable papers and by extension a valuable feature.

3) PLAGIARISM

The word plagiarism, its concept and practice are not new to me going back to my previous studies with internationally accredited schools upholding higher learning principles to meet global academic standards. Ironically students, researchers and employees locally here in my country are not familiar or careless about plagiarism and as such commits plagiarism on a daily basis. EUCLID (2019, 5) stated that: “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” The concept of plagiarism is complex as such has no one standard definition. Universities and colleges have presented differing definitions with examples below:

According to the Rochester Institute of Technology's (RIT) Student Academic Integrity Policy:

Plagiarism is the representation of others' ideas as one's own without giving proper attribution to the original author or authors. Plagiarism occurs when a student copies direct phrases from a text (e.g. books, journals, and internet) and does not provide quotation marks or paraphrases or summarizes those ideas without giving credit to the author or authors. In all cases, if such information is not properly and accurately documented with appropriate credit given, then the student has committed plagiarism.

For purposes of the Stanford University Honor Code:

Plagiarism is defined as the use, without giving reasonable and appropriate credit to or acknowledging the author or source, of another person's original work, whether such work is made up of code, formulas, ideas, language, research, strategies, writing or other form(s). Moreover, verbatim text from another source must always be put in (or within) quotation marks.

Yale College Undergraduate Regulations defines Plagiarism as:

"The use of another's work, words, or ideas without attribution."

Amidst all the many definitions put forward by various authors, the concern is to prevent academic fraud and the violation of somebody else's right no matter the level of material stolen.

The course pack provided for period one selectively and carefully addresses the key areas of not just what plagiarism is, but how it can be avoided in order to write a good paper. The common practice and techniques for citations using the two methods i.e. quotations and paraphrases were clearly outlined and explained. Signal phrasing, I used to do, which was not quite clear until I have gone through the coursepack. Some rules of thumb for writing papers

Writing papers require guidelines and scanning throughout the process. In my previous assignments, when a thesis is approved I go straight into writing. The chapter 3 of course pack on rules of thumb for writing papers introduces me yet to another writing practice. The chapter suggested guidelines on writing papers and some area to be mindful of while writing papers. Papers are written for various purposes i.e. research, financial reports and so on.

Rule of thumb was defined by (Chen 2019) as:

A guideline that provides simplified advice regarding a particular subject. It is a general principle that gives practical instructions for accomplishing or approaching a certain task". He went on to state that "typically, rules of thumb develop as a result of practice and experience rather than from scientific research or theory.

Rule of thumb has to do with guideline suggestions of writing papers that can be applied in varying situations. This practice has characteristics of clearly establishing the main thesis, accessing the importance of the thesis. The rule also emphasizes on clarity in writing your sentences in terms of its length, paragraph length and transitional signals.

The rules further suggest avoiding tedious and clumsy sentences. Sentences should be straight forward, short, precise and clear. For instance, “John was the driver of our car” it can preferably be “John drove our car”. It is fine to have stylistic variety in starting your sentences for example: therefore, moreover, furthermore and so on not to keep repeating words.

Today there are pools of ideas from which one may have a contrary view. In making your views on an idea you have to support your assertion by producing evidences to support your views. Rule guides on when to quote on passage and under which circumstance to quote be clearly outlined in the course pack. The rule cautions “not to submit a paper that strings together lots of quotations” (EUCLID 2019, 15).

The rules emphasize that views discussed should be taken seriously. In that light, it should be noted that philosophers are quite sure of their papers and as sure while attributing your views to them they should not be misinterpreted. In making your views it should be thoroughly evaluated to be sure, otherwise they can be criticized. It is very important that you try as much as possible to be familiar the topic discussed, ensure “develop a sense of its internal integrity” and see if you are able to understand how someone might have come to hold the views in question” (ibid).

4) WHAT IS STYLE GUIDE AND WHY I NEED ONE?

Style guide also called manual is an established standard for writing papers and its designed content. The objective is to aid consistent writing style throughout your documentation. It helps to provide guidelines for different paper writers. Institution adopting style guide is bound to have uniform style and formatting in doing their documents. In my workplace for instance, there is a standard in house style that must be followed to maintain uniformity. Different organizations or professions approve general or specialized style for their audiences for both reading and writing. So is for students, researchers, Scholars, journalism, businesses, government and so on. Using a style guide can help in figuring out the resources that matters in your writing style.

5) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

English language is the official foreign language for all correspondences both spoken and written in my country even though it is not our mother language. The schooling system, the Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) are mandated to do all official communications in English. In school at all levels I studied in English.

Even though there is this awareness across the board in all sectors in me of the slight differences between the American English and that of the British English, much attention has not been given to ensure consistency. “American and British English are both variants of World English” (EUCLID 2019, 27). In a simpler world, English would be written the same way everywhere” (Newell 2015).

As we all speak the same English, there are technical difference pronunciation, spelling, Grammar, and Vocabulary.

Punctuation: Although the word is spelt the same e.g. tomato is pronounced “tom-ah-to” by the British and tom-ya-to by the Americans.

Spelling: for instance: British –Colour and Americans color. Centre by the British and Center by the Americans.

Grammar: Asking someone if he or she has is hungry while that person has just eating. The British will present in the present perfect tense, no, I’ve just eaten already” while the American English uses the past tense, “No, I ate already” which the British sees incorrect.

Vocabulary: There are many differences between the American English and the British English. On that note, there are lots of complications for English learners with mainly the differences in Vocabulary including idioms and phrasal verbs. Some examples in the table below:

British English	American English
Anti-clockwise	Counter-Clockwise
Film	Movie (or Film)
Motorway	Freeway or expressway
queue	line

As can be seen above it is worthwhile to note the differences in both the American and British vocabularies to maintain a consistent witting content.

6) CONCLUSION

This is my first assignment in pursuing my Ph.D. studies in sustainable development and diplomacy. In this session I have been introduce to lots of new concepts and practices that have been time consuming and very difficult to understand. The ACA-401 course pack and video for period one has been very simple, explicate and helpful.

This essay captured five key concepts from the ACA-401 coursepack which includes; essay writing, plagiarism, rules of thumb for academic writing, style guide and the differences between American English and British English. The assignment required me to write an open essay. I chose to write an essay on what I understood from the reading of area of the study pack highlighted above. This session has significantly changed my mindset on writing papers and satisfactorily.

REFERENCES

Chen, James. Rule of Thumb Definition. April 18, 2019. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/r/rule-of-thumb.asp> (accessed August 20, 2020).

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